

1. Planets of the Solar System and Exoplanets

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Planets of the Solar System

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The Solar System

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Rocky Planets and Gas Planets in the Solar System

The four Rocky - Planets
Merkury – Venus – Earth – Mars

The four Gas - Planets
Jupiter – Saturn – Uranus – Neptune
(Dwarf Planet Pluto: degradet today)

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Planets in the Solar System: Distances, Masses and orbital periods

Average distance from the Sun		Mass in units of Earth Mass (EM)	Orbital period around Sun in Earth Years (EY)
Neptune	$4.50 \cdot 10^9$ km	$17.1 \cdot EM$	164.8 EY
Uranus	$2.87 \cdot 10^9$ km	$14.4 \cdot EM$	84.0 EY
Saturn	$1.43 \cdot 10^9$ km	$95.2 \cdot EM$	29.4 EY
Jupiter	$7.78 \cdot 10^8$ km	$317.8 \cdot EM$	11.9 EY
Mars	$2.28 \cdot 10^8$ km	$0.11 \cdot EM$	1.88 EY
Earth	$1.49 \cdot 10^8$ km	$5.97 \cdot 10^{24}$ kg	1
Venus	$1.08 \cdot 10^8$ km	$0.815 \cdot EM$	0.62 EY
Mercury	$5.79 \cdot 10^7$ km	$0.055 \cdot EM$	0.24 EY

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Mean orbital velocity of the Earth around the Sun

In the following we describe the orbit of the Earth E around the Sun S as a circle with the mean radius R (s. Figure below), i.e. we neglect the small eccentricity of the Earth's orbit (see p. 7). The distance traveled by the Earth in one year on the orbit U is then

$$U = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot R \quad 1)$$

With $R = 150'000'000 \text{ km} = 1.5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ km}$, it follows $U = 9.42 \cdot 10^8 \text{ km} = 942 \cdot 10^6 \text{ km} \quad 2)$

The orbital period is $\tau = 1 \text{ year} = 365 \text{ d} = 365 \cdot 24 \text{ h} = 8'760 \text{ h}$. Thus, for the mean orbital velocity v of the Earth around the Sun, it follows:

$$v = U / \tau = 942 \cdot 10^6 \text{ km} / 8'760 \text{ h} \approx 108'000 \text{ km/h} = 30 \text{ km/s} = 108'000 \text{ km/h} \quad 3)$$

Alternatively, v can be calculated by equating the gravitational force F_G and the centrifugal force F_C : If G is the gravitational constant, R is the distance between the Earth and the Sun, $M =$ mass of the Sun, and $m =$ mass of the Earth, then:

$$F_G = G m M / R^2 ; F_C = m (v^2 / R) \quad 4)$$

and from $F_G = F_C$ it follows: $v = \sqrt{G M / R} \quad 5)$

From $G = 6.67 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 / (\text{kg s}^2)$; $M = 1.959 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$ and $R = 1.5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ km}$ it follows:

$$v = 29.74 \text{ km/s} = 107'064 \text{ km/h} \quad 6)$$

in good agreement with equation 3).

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Internal structure of the Earth and Earth magnetic field

internal structure of the Earth

Undisturbed magnetic field of the Earth

The **inner core** of the earth extends between 5'100 km and 6'378 km below the earth's surface. It probably consists of a solid iron-nickel alloy.

The **outer Earth core** lies at a depth between 2'900 km and about 5'100 km below the Earth surface. At a temperature between 3'000 °C and about 5'000 °C this part of the core is liquid. It consists of a nickel-iron melt. In connection with the Earth's rotation, the mobile iron melt is responsible for the **Earth's magnetic field** due to its electrical conductivity.

The Earth magnetic field is very weak (0.2 to 0.7 Gauss). It is also subject to both short and long term fluctuations. The term geomagnetism refers to the magnetic field that can be observed in the immediate vicinity of the Earth and in the absence of external disturbances from the **solar wind** (undisturbed magnetic field). This is in first approximation the field of a **magnetic dipole**. The field extends far out into space. This region of space is also called the **magnetosphere** and is strongly influenced by the solar wind. (see p. 17).

For comparison: The magnetic field of a small bar magnet at a distance of 20 cm is about 0.1 Gauss].

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Numerical excentricity of the planetary orbits around our Sun

The numerical excentricity ϵ of the orbital ellipse of a planet with semiaxes a and b is defined by $\epsilon = (1/a) \cdot (a^2 - b^2)^{1/2}$; if $a = b \rightarrow$ circle $\rightarrow \epsilon = 0$

Properties of Planets

Planet	Diame-ter (km)	Mean velocity (km/h)	Aggre-gate state	Density (g/cm ³)	Duration Of days (in Earth Days)	Min. Temp. (°C)	Max. Temp. (°C)	Slope of the rotation-axis (deg)	Magn. Field (x Earth field) (equator)
Merkury	4'879	172'332	s	5.427	58.65	- 173	427	~ 0	~ 0.01
Venus	12'103	126'072	s	5.243	243.02	+ 437	497	177.36	~ 0
Earth	12'734	107'208	s	5.515	1.00	- 89	58	23.45	1.0
Mars	6'772	86'868	s	3.933	1.026	- 133	27	25.19	~ 0.03
Jupiter	138'346	47'052	g / l / s	1.326	0.413	- 108	- 108	3.13	~ 20
Saturn	114'632	34'884	g / l / s	0.687	0.449	- 139	- 139	26.73	~ 0.7
Uranus	50'532	24'516	g / l / s	1.270	0.718	- 197	- 197	97.77	~ 0.8
Neptune	49'105	19'548	g / l / s	1.638	0.665	- 201	- 201	28.32	~ 0.46

g: gaseous / l: liquid / s: solid

Earth magnetic fields: ca. 60 μ T at Poles, ca. 30 μ T at the equator (1T = 1 Tesla = 10⁴ Gauss)
(The given relative magnetic fields are very approximate)

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Orbital velocities and distances of the Planets from the Sun

The graph shows the velocities of the planets orbiting the Sun. The values are average values, because the planets do not move with constant velocities, but become on their elliptical orbit close to the sun a little faster and in their orbit far from the Sun a little slower. The fundamental laws for the orbits of the planets around the sun are descended from J. Kepler (see Reference R.1.9, p. 1-9).

Together with the Figure below, we can see that the further away from the Sun the planets travel, the slower they travel.

Mercury as the innermost planet is the fastest with the gigantic speed of 172'000 km/h, Neptune as the outermost planet is much slower with just under 20'000 km/h. [The planet Neptune is still 100 times faster than a car driving with 200 km/h !].

Planets in interstellar Space

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Planets in the Milky Way and the Universe

Almost everything is orbited by planets !

Artist's impression;
European Southern Observatory
(ESO)

In our own Galaxy, the Milkyway, about 200 billion stars exist, and in the whole observable Universe there are still a few hundred billion other Galaxies. How many planets can we expect now?. As of January 4, 2021, a year before the beginning of this work, about 4'396 exoplanets in 3'242 systems were known, although some objects have masses in the range of brown dwarfs [(brown dwarfs are celestial bodies that occupy a special position between stars and planets)]. So the most massive object in the "Extrasolar Planets Encyclopedia" has 81 Jupiter masses M_j .

The planet TOI-849 b is almost as large as Neptune, but it is not a gas giant. This can be inferred from the fact that TOI 849 b is an exposed planetary core. According to Dr. Armstrong, this is the first time that an intact exposed core of a gas giant has been discovered around a Star. According to Dr. Modarsini of the University of Bern, two theories are possible: either: the shell of the original gas planet was lost or it was never there.

720 multiplanetary systems have up to 8 detected planets. Planetary systems are considered today in the immediate vicinity of the Stars as a safely proven, generally spread phenomenon. Investigations and measurements of the "Institut astrophysique de Paris" showed that a Star of the Milky Way has, in the average, one to two planets.

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Some important Earth-like exoplanets

Scientists have recently discovered two new planets, Kepler-62e and Kepler-62f (see p. 13), orbiting their star Kepler-62 at a distance of 1'200 light-years (!) from Earth. The figure also shows the planets Earth and Mars in the upper right. The planets Kepler-62e and Kepler-62f are the smallest exoplanets discovered by the Kepler mission.

The numbers attached to the planets (e.g. 0.82 for Kepler-62e) are the so-called ESI values (Earth Similarity Index), which are a measure for the similarity of the planets to Earth [ESI(Earth) = 1, ESI(Kepler-62e) = 0.82]. The value of ESI depends on the radius of the planet, on its mean density, on its escape velocity and on its surface temperature.

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Gliese and Kepler exoplanet systems

Exoplanet Gliese 832 c and the Earth

Gliese 832c is an exoplanet that orbits the red dwarf Gliese 832. It was discovered in 2014 by a team led by the Australian astronomer Robert A. Wittenmeyer from the University of New South Wales. The planet Gliese 832c is located in the habitable zone.

Gliese 832c has a minimum mass of about 5.4 Earth masses and is classified as a super-Earth. The planet orbits its central star in nearly 36 days on a slightly eccentric path that runs partly in the habitable zone of Gliese 832. Earth-like temperatures could prevail on Gliese 832c.

Exoplanet Kepler-62 e and 6 2f and our Earth

Using the Kepler telescope, a Washington University astronomer, Eric Agol, discovered what is believed to be one of the most Earth-like exoplanets, Kepler-62e.

Its planetary sibling, Kepler 62f, was later discovered by a research team from the NASA Ames Research Center.

Although the masses and densities of these two planets are not yet known, Agol has pioneered the so-called "Transit Timing Variation" method, by which the masses of such planets can be evaluated in the future.

1-13

Earth-like planet Tau Ceti e

Discovered in 2012, the fourth - but still unconfirmed - planet Tau Ceti e, orbiting the star Tau Ceti, has an "Earth Similarity Index, ESI" of 0.78; that's more than Mars' index of 0.697, the most Earth-like planet in our solar system. Tau Ceti e, which orbits its sun once in 168 days, is a little larger than Earth, which by definition has a (highest) value of 1. However, it has a sweaty surface temperature of 68 °C (the corresponding value of the Earth is 16 °C).

Illustration of the exoplanet Tau Ceti e.

As with its neighboring planet TauCeti f, the probability that extraterrestrial life has developed there is rather small. But Tau Ceti e is the closest known exoplanet to our planet. The Tau Ceti system is only 12 light-years away from the Earth - in cosmic dimensions this is one house number further in the same street. For us it is nevertheless unreachably far away. For comparison: The moon is only 1.3 light seconds away from the Earth.

Appendix: Chapter 1

A-1-0

The_Van Allen Radiation Belt

The Van Allen radiation belt (named after the US astrophysicist James Van Allen) is a ring (torus) of energy-rich charged particles trapped by the Earth's magnetic field. Until now it was assumed that these particles originate mainly from the solar wind and cosmic rays. However, recent investigations of the probes "Van-Allen A" and "Van-Allen B" have shown that the majority of the particles originate in the belt itself, where atoms are virtually torn apart by electromagnetic fields and electrons are thus released.

The belt consists essentially of two radiation zones: The inner of them extends at low latitudes in a range of about 700 to 6'000 km above the Earth's surface and consists mainly of high-energy protons. The second one is located 15'000 to 25'000 km altitude and contains mainly electrons.

Significance for space flight: The intensity of the radiation within the Van Allen belt can reach values that are hazardous to health, both spatially and temporally. Therefore, the aspect of radiation protection must not be neglected for manned space missions in Earth orbit.

A-1-1

A-1-0 / A-1-1

Temporal evolution of the exoplanets discovered

Number of exoplanets discovered per year (as of 26, January 2019)									
1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997
1	1	0	0	3	0	0	3	7	0
1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
9	11	22	15	31	28	33	34	34	60
2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
62	89	126	196	161	199	846	184	1474	149
2018	2019	Total: 3971 exoplanets							
190	5								

By early 2021, approximately 4'660 exoplanets had been discovered. (see Ref. A-1-2 b)

A-1-2

A-1-2

Referenzen: Kapitel 1

R-1-0

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